

Research Article

A Portable Thermoelectric Bottle for Dual Heating and Cooling with Integrated Hydration Tracking System

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Abstract: Hydration is critical for maintaining health, yet modern lifestyles often lead to poor water consumption habits. This study presents the design and development of a smart water bottle integrating heating, cooling, hydration reminders, and real-time temperature display into a portable, rechargeable solution. The product promotes sustainable practices through the use of eco-friendly materials and alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). A thermoelectric module for heating and cooling, coupled with a digital sensor and hydration tracking system to enhance user experience. This innovation is particularly relevant to individuals with active lifestyles and regions with variable climates, supporting health and well-being.

Keywords: Thermoelectric module; heating and cooling technology; hydration monitoring; smart water bottle; temperature control

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1. INTRODUCTION

Innovative approaches, like thermoelectric modules, offer a promising way to develop water bottles that can heat and cool liquids effectively. Integrating digital hydration tracking systems and real-time temperature displays can help promote healthy hydration habits, especially for people who lead active lifestyles. This approach provides a sustainable solution that improves daily life. This study is about creating a smart water bottle that combines various features into a convenient and easy-to-use product.

1.1 Problem Statement

Staying properly hydrated is very important for our health and well-being. However, many people find it difficult to drink enough water because they have busy schedules, forget to drink, or do not have easy access to drinks that are at the right temperature. Current water bottles do not have multiple functions that can meet various needs, such as heating for hot beverages, cooling for refreshing drinks, and monitoring water consumption. The difference is especially noticeable in places where

people lead active lifestyles and in areas with changing weather, as it can be hard to find hot or cold water when needed. Furthermore, many products available today are not environmentally friendly, as they lead to waste due to single-use plastics and designs that are not energy-efficient. To tackle these challenges, we need a new product that combines thermoelectric temperature control, hydration reminders, and real-time temperature monitoring. It should also be eco-friendly, portable, and designed with the user in mind. This would improve personal hydration practices and also support the ideas of sustainability and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

1.2 Objectives

This research aims to develop a smart water bottle capable of:

1. Heating and cooling water using a compact thermoelectric module.
2. Displaying real-time water temperature.
3. Providing hydration reminders through a built-in notification system.
4. Supporting sustainability by utilizing eco-friendly materials and USB-rechargeable lithium-ion batteries.

1.3 SDG Relevance

The project supports SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) by promoting hydration awareness and its eco-conscious design aligns with SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 System Overview

The Portable Water Bottle Heating and Cooling System is designed to maintain the temperature of liquids using thermoelectric technology. This system combines Thermoelectric Coolers (TECs), Thermoelectric Generators (TEGs), a temperature sensor, an Arduino microcontroller, and a lithium-ion battery to efficiently heat or cool the water inside the bottle. The following sections describe the detailed components and materials used in constructing this innovative bottle.

2.2 Thermoelectric Modules (TEM)

The system utilizes TECs and TEGs to create a temperature difference through the Peltier effect. TECs facilitate the heating and cooling processes by causing one side of the module to cool while the opposite side heats up when electric current flows through the junction of two different conductors. TEGs, in turn, help in energy harvesting to maintain the energy efficiency of the system. This is based on the Peltier effect (The Peltier effect is the reverse phenomenon of the Seebeck effect; the electrical current flowing through the junction connecting two materials will emit or absorb heat per unit time at the junction to balance the difference in the chemical potential of the two materials), where an electric current passing through a junction of two different conductors creates a cooling effect on one side and heating on the other.

2.3 Temperature Sensing

The DS18B20 is a flexible digital thermometer that uses 1-Wire technology and allows for programmable resolution. It is suitable for use in a heating and cooling water bottle to give accurate temperature readings in real-time. The device provides a broad temperature range from -55°C to $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$, with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ between -10°C and $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$. This ensures accurate monitoring of the temperature of the liquid. The DS18B20 uses a 1-Wire bus for communication, which makes the design easier because it only needs one data line and a ground connection to communicate with a microprocessor. This sensor is designed to measure temperature and can be set to different resolutions between 9 and 12 bits. The standard setting is 12 bits, which allows for a small change in temperature of 0.0625°C .

The capability to function in parasite power mode, which allows it to draw power from the data line, is especially advantageous for compact designs such as water bottles. This feature minimises the requirement for extra wiring. The DS18B20 also has programmable alarm functions that allow users to set upper and lower temperature limits. This feature helps in providing safety alerts for temperatures that are too high or too low. Every DS18B20 sensor comes with a distinct 64-bit serial code. This feature enables several sensors to operate on the same 1-Wire bus, which is beneficial for more complicated applications or potential product enhancements. The features of the DS18B20 make it a very good option for measuring temperature in your heating and cooling water bottle project.

2.4 Control Unit

An Arduino microcontroller is central to the system's operation, processing the temperature data from the DS18B20 sensor. The Arduino compares the real-time temperature with a predefined set point and sends signals to the TECs to either heat or cool the water. This automated control ensures consistent temperature regulation.

2.5 Power Supply

The thermoelectric smart bottle leverages the advantages of lithium-ion battery technology to ensure efficient and reliable operation. One of the key benefits of lithium-ion batteries is their customizable operating voltage, which can be tailored through insertion reactions to meet the specific power requirements of the thermoelectric module and digital components. This flexibility allows the smart bottle to achieve optimal performance for both heating and cooling functions while maintaining energy efficiency. The inclusion of lithium-ion batteries also enhances portability and usability, as these batteries are known for their high energy density, excellent charge–discharge cycle performance, and reliable operation under varied conditions. With extended operational life, lithium-ion batteries are widely used in a wide range of industries, such as electrified marine transportation systems, stationary energy storage systems, electric propulsion in space, and electric mobility (Wang, 2025). By integrating lithium-ion technology, the product ensures a sustainable, high-performance power source that supports its innovative features and aligns with eco-friendly practices.

2.6 User Interface

The system incorporates an LED indicator to provide visual feedback on the operational status, indicating whether the bottle is in heating or cooling mode. This feature enhances user interaction by providing real-time system updates.

2.7 Heat Dissipation

To ensure the thermoelectric modules operate efficiently and prevent overheating, the system includes heat sinks made of aluminum or copper. These materials are chosen for their excellent thermal conductivity, which aids in the effective dissipation of heat from the TECs

2.8 Material Composition

The materials selected for constructing the bottle are crucial for its functionality, durability, and safety:

- **Outer Shell:** 304 stainless steel is used for its durability, corrosion resistance, and thermal retention properties. It also ensures that the water's taste remains unaffected.
- **Silicone Coating:** For easier handling and gripping of the water bottle.
- **Insulation Layer:** Polyurethane foam insulation is used to reduce heat transfer, while some models may incorporate vacuum insulation to enhance thermal retention.
- **Thermoelectric Module Housing:** Lightweight metals like aluminum or durable plastics provide structural integrity and facilitate heat dissipation.
- **Seals and Gaskets:** Food-grade silicone or rubber ensures airtight seals to maintain the bottle's insulation and prevent leaks.
- **Electronics Housing:** Durable plastic or metal enclosures protect the electronic components from environmental factors.
- **Active Buzzer:** Connects through arduino to remind users about water consumption.
- **Lithium-ion Batteries:** Rechargeable batteries for long lasting usage.
- **3D1C Integrated Circuit:** Control heating and cooling by managing the thermoelectric elements to heat and cool the water, as well as efficiently regulating power delivery from lithium-ion batteries.

2.9 Cooling and Heating Duration

The time required to cool or heat the water depends on several factors, including the power of the thermoelectric modules, initial water temperature, ambient temperature, and volume of water. Generally, higher power TECs and efficient heat dissipation mechanisms can achieve faster temperature changes.

2.10 Food-Grade Materials

All materials in contact with the liquid are food-grade to ensure user safety.

- **Stainless Steel (304 or 316):** Used for its non-reactive properties and ease of cleaning.
- **BPA-Free Plastics:** Used for components like the lid or outer casing, ensuring no harmful chemicals leach into the water (Brent, 2023).
- **Food-Grade Silicone:** Utilized for seals and gaskets to prevent leaks and maintain hygiene.

This combination of advanced thermoelectric technology, durable materials, and user-friendly design makes the Portable Water Bottle Heating and Cooling System an effective solution for maintaining the desired temperature of beverages on the go.

2.11 Time Estimation for Heating and Cooling Water Using a TEC1-12706 Peltier Module (Theory)

a. Peltier Module Performance

- Heat Transfer Rate: Approximately 50 W under ideal conditions with appropriate heat sinks.
- Efficiency: Estimated between 10-15% in practical setups due to real-world inefficiencies.

b. Water Properties

- Specific Heat Capacity of Water: 4.18 J/g°C.
- Density of Water: Approximately 1 g/mL.

c. Bottle Volume

- Assumed to be 500 mL for this calculation.

d. Temperature Change

- Heating: Increasing water temperature from 25°C to 60°C ($\Delta T = 35^\circ\text{C}$).
- Cooling: Decreasing water temperature from 25°C to 10°C ($\Delta T = 15^\circ\text{C}$).

e. Calculations

Energy Required to Heat or Cool Water

The formula for calculating the energy required is:

$$Q = m \cdot c \cdot \Delta T$$

Where:

- Q = energy required (in Joules),
- m = mass of water (500 mL = 500 g),
- c = specific heat capacity of water (4.18 J/g°C),
- ΔT = temperature change.

1. Heating:

$$Q = 500 \cdot 4.18 \cdot 35 = 73,150 \text{ J}$$

2. Cooling:

$$Q = 500 \cdot 4.18 \cdot 15 = 31,350 \text{ J}$$

Time Required:

$$t = Q/P$$

Where:

- t = time (seconds),
- P = power supplied (W).

Using a Peltier module with 50 W heat transfer:

- Heating: $t=73,15050 \approx 1,463$ seconds (~24 minutes)
- Cooling: $t=31,35050 \approx 627$ seconds (~10.5 minutes)

f. Recommendations

i. Ideal Water Volume

- For faster heating and cooling, consider reducing the water volume to 250-300 mL. This will significantly reduce the required energy and time, effectively halving them.

ii. Efficiency Enhancements

- Insulation: Use better insulation around the water container to minimize heat exchange with the surroundings, thus improving the efficiency.
- Heat Sinks and Fans: Install efficient heat sinks and fans to enhance the dissipation of heat from the Peltier module.

iii. Practical Expectations

- In real-world conditions, the actual times might be slightly longer due to inefficiencies in heat transfer and power supply.

g. Performance Factors Influencing Heating and Cooling Time

The heating and cooling time is influenced by several factors:

- Power of Thermoelectric Modules: The higher the power, the faster the process.
- Initial Water Temperature: Starting temperature of the water significantly affects the time needed.
- Water Volume: Larger volumes require more energy and time.
- Ambient Temperature: Higher ambient temperatures can slow down cooling processes.
- Heat Dissipation Efficiency: Efficient heat dissipation mechanisms reduce the time required.
- User-defined Settings: Custom settings, such as desired final temperature, affect the time needed.

h. Estimated Time Range

Based on these factors, the heating and cooling time can range from a few minutes to over an hour, depending on the specific setup and conditions.

3. FINDINGS

The level of hydration and the way fluids are consumed can greatly affect how well adolescents think and perform mentally. A study carried out in Petaling Perdana, Malaysia, found that more than half of the adolescent participants were either mildly or moderately dehydrated, with a percentage of 59.6%. In contrast, only 33% of the participants were considered well-hydrated. The cognitive performance of well-hydrated adolescents was notably better, with an average score of 100.38 ± 12.01 , while dehydrated individuals had an average score of 92.00 ± 13.63 (Tung et al., 2020).

The research emphasised that plain water is the main source of hydration, with an average intake of 877.00 ± 492.08 mL per day. This is followed by malted drinks and sweetened juice beverages. However, beverages that contain added sugars, like soft drinks and sweetened tea, were frequently consumed and linked to adverse effects on cognitive function. Regression analysis showed that soft drinks ($\beta = -0.009$; $P < 0.05$) and sweetened tea ($\beta = -0.019$; $P < 0.05$) are important negative factors affecting cognitive scores. Even though it is suggested that individuals should drink between 2,000 and 2,200 mL of fluids each day, only 29.6% of the participants met this guideline (Tung et al., 2020). This shows that there is a significant difference in hydration habits among adolescents.

Hydration plays a crucial role in various bodily functions, including regulating temperature, supporting cognitive processes, maintaining kidney function, aiding digestion, and promoting healthy skin. Insufficient water intake can lead to adverse health outcomes such as impaired cognitive function, fatigue, headaches, increased risk of kidney stones, and constipation. Mild dehydration, defined as a loss of more than 2% of body weight, is commonly associated with fatigue and decreased alertness. Proper hydration supports key cognitive functions, enhancing memory, attention, and mood (Liska et al., 2019). Acute water intake has been shown to improve visual attention and episodic memory, highlighting its importance in maintaining mental performance.

The amount of water a person should drink each day can differ due to various reasons, such as their gender, how active they are, the climate they live in, and any health issues they may have. Healthline states that the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine recommend that men should drink around 3.7 litres (15.5 cups) of water each day, whereas women should target about 2.7 litres (11.5 cups). These guidelines encompass all liquids obtained from both drinks and food items. However, certain situations such as intense physical activity, hot climates, or specific health issues may require a higher intake of water. The "8x8" rule, which suggests that individuals should drink eight 8-ounce glasses of water each day, is a well-known guideline. However, it may not suit everyone. Indicators that show whether a person is properly hydrated include feeling thirsty and checking the colour of urine. If the urine is pale yellow, it means hydration is good, while darker urine suggests that more fluids are needed (Gunnars, 2023).

Table 1. Guidelines of daily water intake

ASPECT	DETAILS
Recommended Daily Intake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Men: 3.7 liters (15.5 cups) • Women: 2.7 liters (11.5 cups)
Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes all fluids from beverages and food
Factors Affecting Intake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity • Climate (hot weather increases need) • Overall health (e.g., fever, infections)
Special Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intense exercise • Hot climates • Certain health conditions

8×8 Rule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common guideline (eight 8-ounce glasses of water daily) but not suitable for everyone
Practical Hydration Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thirst • Urine color: Pale yellow indicates good hydration; darker urine suggests more water is needed

Based on the LaFata research, compared to drinking room-temperature water (22°C), drinking cold water (4°C) during exercise reduced the rate at which body temperature rose. Compared to those who drank room-temperature water (1.13°C), those who drank cold water had a lesser increase in core temperature (0.83°C). This indicates that while they were exercising, cold water kept their bodies colder for longer. About half of the participants performed better when using cold water for certain activity categories, such as leaping and endurance (time to fatigue on a bike). These gains, nevertheless, weren't substantial enough to qualify as statistically significant. In contrast, individuals who drank room-temperature water did somewhat better on the bench press test, although the difference was negligible. By the end of the workout, both groups—those consuming room-temperature and cold water—were dehydrated. This demonstrates that although cold water aids in temperature regulation, dehydration may still occur if insufficient water intake is maintained.

4. DISCUSSION

The results highlight the important necessity for measures to encourage adequate hydration and decrease the consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs). The thermoelectric heating and cooling bottle meets this requirement by providing features that enhance the appeal of plain water and nutritious beverages. The ability to regulate the temperature of liquids makes water more attractive in different climates, leading people to prefer water instead of sugar-sweetened beverages. The device also has hydration timers and consumption trackers. These features help monitor hydration effectively, which is important for keeping cognitive performance at its best. The bottle includes notifications and reminders that assist users in staying hydrated at regular intervals. This feature helps improve mental clarity and decreases the chances of experiencing fatigue and mood issues that can be associated with dehydration. The bottle can heat and cool liquids, which makes it useful for various needs. It can also help teach young people about the importance of staying hydrated.

This innovation is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals, especially Goal 3, which focusses on Good Health and Well-being, and Goal 12, which emphasises Responsible Consumption and Production. Encouraging people to drink more water helps reduce the waste created by single-use beverage containers, which promotes responsible consumption. Staying hydrated has several health benefits. It can improve cognitive function and overall well-being, which helps in promoting good health. Additionally, the bottle can keep drinks at the desired temperatures, which increases its usefulness by making it more pleasant to stay hydrated. Drinking cold water is important for regulating body temperature during exercise. It helps manage core body temperature and can delay feelings of fatigue caused by heat, especially in moderate to hot climates. Cold water might not have a major impact on power or strength exercises, but it can help with temperature regulation, which is beneficial for endurance activities. This thermoelectric bottle provides a new and eco-friendly way to stay hydrated. It helps people drink more water while also encouraging care for the environment and healthier habits in the community. With this, based on the research the modelling of the product is depicted as below Figure 1, that visualizes the 3D concept of the water bottle, as well as Figure 2 that visualizes the 2D concept of the water bottle.

Figure 1. 3D prototype of the Temper water bottle

Figure 2. 2D prototype of the Temper water bottle.

5. CONCLUSION

The thermoelectric heating and cooling bottle helps people stay hydrated and also reduces the need for sugary drinks. It provides features like temperature control, hydration timers, and consumption tracking, which help ensure regular water intake and enhance cognitive performance and

overall health. This device supports Sustainable Development Goals by promoting responsible consumption and minimising waste from single-use containers. Moreover, its capacity to control core body temperature while exercising makes it an important resource for improving endurance and comfort in different weather conditions. The thermoelectric bottle is a new and eco-friendly option that helps people stay hydrated and encourages healthier habits in their daily lives.

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References

- Brent A. Bauer, M. D. (2023, March 24). *Tips to reduce BPA exposure*. Mayo Clinic. Retrieved from: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/healthy-lifestyle/nutrition-and-healthy-eating/expert-answers/bpa/f aq-20058331>.
- Gunnars, K. (2023, June 5). *How much water should you drink per day?* Healthline. Retrieved from: <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/how-much-water-should-you-drink-per-day#effects>.
- LaFata, D., Carlson-Phillips, A., Sims, S. T., & Russell, E. M. (2012). The effect of a cold beverage during an exercise session combining both strength and energy systems development training on core temperature and markers of performance. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1550-2783-9-44>.
- Lin, J., Zhao, S., Jervis, R., & Shearing, P. (2024). Probing the electrochemical processes of niobium pentoxides (NB2O5) for high-rate lithium-ion batteries: A Review. *ChemElectroChem*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.202300581>.
- Liska, D., Mah, E., Brisbois, T., Barrios, P. L., Baker, L. B., & Spriet, L. L. (2019). Narrative review of hydration and selected health outcomes in the general population. *Nutrients*, 11(1), 70. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11010070>.
- Maxim Integrated. (2019). DS18B20. *DS18B20 Datasheet and Product Info | Analog Devices*. Retrieved from: <https://www.analog.com/en/products/ds18b20.html>.
- Tung, S. E., Ch'ng, Y. Z., Karnan, T. V., Chong, P. N., Zubaidah, J. O., & Chin, Y. S. (2020). Fluid intake, hydration status and its association with cognitive function among adolescents in Petaling Perdana, Selangor, Malaysia. *Nutrition Research and Practice*, 14(5), 490. <https://doi.org/10.4162/nrp.2020.14.5.490>.
- Wang, Z., Song, Y., Zhao, Q., Shi, B., He, J., & Li, J. (2025). Unveiling the electrochemical degradation behavior of 18650 lithium-ion batteries involved different humidity conditions. *Journal of Power Sources*, 630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.236185>.